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HOW DO WOMEN EXPERIENCE AN ALTERNATIVE EDUCATIONAL MODEL IN IT?

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ABSTRACT

The advancement of technology, the need for life-long learning driven by the constantly emerging demands of contemporary economy, as well as the necessity for the educational organisations to address increasing competition and economy crises compel the transformation of education models; hence the emergence of alternative models of education. Such alternative models target different categories of learners and show various levels of success. This paper is an effort to contribute to the study of women's experience of an unconventional educational model recently launched in the field of Computer Science, namely at a franchisee of École 42 in Russia. The said model draws upon peer pedagogy, gamification, cross-generational and family friendly-learning. This study investigates the response of women participating in the program to the aforementioned methods. Recommendations produced based on the study may contribute to more efficient adaptation of the alternative model under study to women's needs and thus to female student retention.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education systems and related organizations have always adapted to the developments and changes of economy and technologies; perhaps now these changes are more frequent and rapid, hence the demand of more often and quick responses from the side of those involved in education [1]-[3]. Alternative education models represent one way educators address the said demand. Contemporary alternative education models come in a variety of forms [4]-[6], aiming to effectively cater to the needs of both labor markets and learners, as well as to address organizational existential and economic crises of educational organizations. One of such recently emerged alternative forms of educational organization is École 42, launched in France in 2013 and now represented in over 20 countries [7], including Russia since 2018, where currently two branches operate – one in Moscow, and one in Kazan. The School trains manpower exclusively for IT industry, tuition free. The unique approach of the School is that it heavily relies on peer pedagogy, which is stated as studying without professors¹. The School's methodology is also based on the principles and practices of gamification, cross-generational learning, and family friendly-learning.

Peer pedagogy used by École 42 draws upon *social constructivism* approach and the concept of *active learning*, e.g., [8], in particular. It implies that students learn from each other in formal and informal settings with various levels of supervision. This approach has long been used in higher education in general, e.g., [9]-[11], and in teaching Computer Science related subjects in particular, e.g., [12]-[14]. Findings on the effect of such practices on learning gain are generally positive, though the need for the instructors', course designers', and mentors' professional development is highlighted.

Gamification in education setups and *challenge-based education* have been a subject of multiple studies, e.g., [15]-[18], [19]-[21], respectively. Zahedi et al. in [22] have investigated gamification in education for computer science students. They concluded that 'gamification is a gender-neutral learning engagement strategy that improves female students' performance as much as male students'. Besides, the results show no or little positive effect on women's interest and engagement in the field of Computer Science. Jent and Janneck [23] have studied the influence of gender and age on motivation enhancement via gamification. They concluded that male users feel more motivated by gamification than female participants. Moreover, motivation through gamification decreases with age.

Further, Glebocki et al. in [24] discuss the value of *cross-generational* learning setup and argue that IT transmedia blend is supposed to bridge the gap between generations. Rubin et al. in [25] investigated how age and gender predict the deep learning ability and satisfaction at the university. They showed that age predicted deep learning ability more strongly among women than among men. Moreover, age positively predicted degree satisfaction among women but not among men, and deep learning mediated this moderation effect. Finally, to the best of our knowledge, *family-friendly learning environment* topic requires more intensive study, while the literature on workplace family-friendly policies is considerably large. The body of

¹ <https://www.42.us.org/program/peer-to-peer-learning/>

available literature, though limited, describes the examples of existing family-friendly learning environments and resources at the universities and investigates the challenges parenting students have to address; the results show the demand to acknowledge the need to develop and use official policies for this group of students [26]-[28].

Combining the aforementioned concepts, the novel approach of École 42 should clearly be investigated and understood for the benefit of learners, IT industry, and education research. In the current research effort, which is a part of an ongoing study of the said alternative model implementation by a franchisee of École 42 in Russia, we opted to investigate female students experiences and perceptions of the School's model. In particular, this research seeks to:

1. compare students' enrolment, learning progress, and dropout data by gender and age group to understand how much academic progress is related to the students' age, specifically for female students.
2. investigate how women perceive peer learning pedagogy, gamification, cross-generational learning practices and if family-friendly learning environment is important for the students of the educational model of the School under study.

The rest of the paper takes a form of two sections. Section Methodology briefly describes data collection methods, section Results and Discussion details and interprets the collected data.

2 METHODOLOGY

The data for this study were obtained from two sources in 2020 and 2021. First, the data on enrolment, academic progress, dropout rates, gender and age, as well as places of residence of the School's applicants and students for this study were provided by the School's administration. The data were anonymized. Specifically, the data were provided on the pass/fail results and gender for the selection activities for 6099 program applicants in Moscow branch and 1979 program applicants in Kazan branch (both are cities in Russia). Academic achievements, dropouts, gender and the place of residence for the enrolled students were available for both Moscow and Kazan branches. Kazan branch administration also provided the data on the students' age. In addition, in spring 2021 all female students of the School were invited to participate in an online in-house designed survey. The survey responses were anonymous. We obtained 208 unique responses by this survey, which is around 29% of current female student body of the School.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Composition of the School's students population

In this subsection we present the relevant data and compare

- the selection results in Moscow and Kazan branches for women and men (Table 1)
- dropout results for men and women, by enrolment batch (Table 2)
- the distribution of students in Kazan branch by gender and age group (Fig. 1)

- dropout results in Kazan branch by gender and age group (Fig. 2)
- the distribution of the students in Moscow and Kazan branches by gender and the geographical distance to the place of students' residence (Fig. 3)
- the relation of the geographical distance and student retention in Moscow office (Fig. 4)

To begin with, the School employs a comprehensive process for the students selection. Table 1 shows that during the selection process, on average, female applicants perform slightly better than their male peers.

Table 1. Shares of enrolled applicants by gender, %.

Branch	women	men
Moscow	45%	41%
Kazan	32%	29%

It is important to note though, that men tend to perform better than women during studies: the highest Level that can be achieved in the program is 21; and, while the highest achieved Level in men is Level 20, for women it is significantly lower - Level 15. To date, the highest achieved levels belong to the students of the first enrollment batch and the results can alter with time. To date, men systematically demonstrate higher achieved levels: in all enrollment batches without exception their average scores are higher, including when calculated on a sample truncated by 5%. At the same time, the median performance values for women and men are identical in all enrollment waves (except for wave 3, where the difference is 1 point: Level 7 for men and Level 6 for women).

Further, for the enrolled students the average dropout rates for women and men are almost similar - 37% and 33% respectively, and the tendency of dropouts of women being slightly higher than those of men holds for individual batches, with the only significant difference of the said rates for batch 1 and a reverse result for batch 6 in Moscow (Table 2). Batches 6 and 7 are recent, hence lower dropout rates to date in general.

Table 2. Students' dropout by gender and enrolment batches, %.

Batch	Women	Men
1 Moscow	44%	28%
2 Moscow	38%	35%
3 Moscow	52%	48%
4 Moscow	38%	35%
5 Kazan	36%	35%
6 Moscow	15%	16%
7 Kazan	17%	11%

Figs. 1 and 2 show the distribution of female and male students in Kazan branch by age group and their dropout rates, respectively. Students' age in this branch currently vary from 19 to 61. However, around half of both male and female students belong to the age group of 20 to 25 years old; the second biggest age group for both

sexes is 26-30 years old. Notably, the shares of women in the age groups of 26-30 and 31-35 years old are bigger than the shares of men of these age groups. This might mean that women more than men perceive this program as an option of career change. As for the comparison of dropout rates of women and men (Fig. 2), in the largest age groups women tend to drop out more frequently than men. Interestingly, so far older female students show more persistence. Thus, it could be worthwhile for the School to test this hypothesis and focus mor women 35+ years.

Fig. 1. Shares of women and men in student population of Kazan branch by age group, %

Fig. 2. Students' dropout rates in Kazan branch by gender and age groups, %.

Fig. 3 compares student bodies in Moscow and Kazan in terms of geographical distance of their place of residence from the study site. Notably, whereas the student body in Moscow is mostly represented by the locals, Kazan branch welcomes significantly more students who come from quite remote places. This might be due to Kazan being more affordable to reside while studying or due to more options of remote learning in this branch. Notably, the share of women arriving from the distance over 500km is larger than that of men for both locations: 33% vs 27% in

Moscow, and 51% vs 37% in Kazan. This may indicate a higher motivation of female students to study.

Fig. 3. Shares of male and female students in Moscow and Kazan branches by the distance to the location of residence from the study site, %.

Regarding the relation of student dropout rate and the distance from the original place of residence to the study site, on Moscow branch student population we observed (Fig. 4) that females who arrived from over 500-3000 km have lower dropout rate than their male peers, though overall dropout rate is higher for females. This may imply higher motivation of women arrived from long distance to study. Only few students arrived from 3000+km, hence the statistics for this group is not reliable.

Fig. 4. Comparison of dropout rates of female and male students in Moscow branch by the distance to the location of residence from the study site, %.

To conclude, based on the obtained data, the School's model attracts a significant number of women, though so far women of the largest age groups of the target population tend to drop out more often than men. This tendency is, however, with the exception of women aged 35+ who at the moment of data collection showed zero dropout rate; clearly, such students are fewer, but, though generalizations might be

premature at the moment, the hypothesis might be worth testing. In the following section, based on the survey data, we report the revealed perceptions of female students' of the School pedagogies and further discuss possible ways of their attraction and retention.

3.2 The effect of peer-pedagogy, gamification, cross-generation learning, family friendly-learning on female student retention.

The perception of the pedagogies employed by the School were studied by way of analyses of textual and numerical data collected via an in-house designed survey filled in only by female students (Appendix 1).

Peer pedagogy used by the School in practice means the absence of regular professors and scheduled classes. The majority of the students positively perceive a setup with no professors, though the share of this challenge with the students who dropped out reached almost 50% of the responses (Table 3). The results of our previous study (unpublished to date) revealed that female students having prior knowledge related to IT obtained in degree and non-degree programs experience no such a challenge.

Another theme, also observed in textual responses to the open question “*Are there any other downsides or anything that needs to be changed in School 21, in addition to those mentioned above?*”, is that a noticeable number of women reported the need to moderate discussion forum, which is an essential part of peer pedagogy, because of unwanted sexist and offensive comments towards women. An example of a related comment:

*There are some peers at our school who treat women badly, not just in IT, but women in general. They express dislike and doubt the abilities of girls online, it is very unpleasant to read, it is demoralizing. After these messages, you don't feel very safe when there are such inadequate people in the public space. I wish there was a way to block inadequate aggressive peers in Slack. Specifically the peer with the nickname **** -- who makes posts with messages against women.*

Table 3. Challenges of the program reported by those dropped out and currently studying.

Challenges	Share of respondents	
	Dropped out (N54)	Currently studying(N154)
Motivation loss	52%	27%
The projects are too complex, requiring higher level of prerequisite knowledge	48%	36%
The projects are too time-consuming	48%	45%
Absence of full time instructors/mentors	43%	30%
Strict Deadlines	35%	41%
Lack of interesting tracks	31%	21%
Separation from main job or family	31%	21%
Unfriendly treatment from other students or administration	30%	21%
Unclear grading system	22%	14%

Challenges	Share of respondents	
	Dropped out (N54)	Currently studying(N154)
Loss of interest to IT career	19%	1%
Accommodation issues	9%	19%
No support in internship search	7%	8%
No support during the internship	2%	3%
Other	2%	7%
None	0%	2%

It looks like women consider these problems fixable and tend to disapprove the idea of women-only batches. Besides, a lot of textual responses appreciate peers and the opportunity to collaborate with them as they are perceived as a trigger of motivation:

Students working next to each other (peers) also motivate you to work hard, to find interesting and faster solutions together (although occasionally there was the opposite effect, when they distracted each other).

Gamification practices at the School are manifested by sequencing the complexity and the progress by levels, by setting strict deadlines and assigning points for the quality and timely completion of the assignments. Naturally, we observed stronger dissatisfaction with the deadlines requirements and grading system with the dropped out students (Table 3).

Some students notice the limitations of deadlines:

... the level of cheating and superficially and unfairly executed projects, often caused by, excuse me, screwed up deadlines or the desire to score points ..

However, other students highlighted the positive effect of deadlines on their learning:

Free schedule, but at the same time deadlines do not allow you to procrastinate long with projects... There is more freedom, but also more responsibility - we don't owe anything to anyone, and the future of our careers depends on ourselves, that's what I liked the most!

[The School gives] an opportunity to become a more disciplined and organized person.

One suggestion for modification of the deadlines system is:

Each participant should determine their own deadlines. If they are motivated, they will work towards their goal at a pace that is comfortable for them. If a person is not making progress, they are already punishing themselves by the lack of progress. Punitive deadlines are useless - demotivating.

Besides, students suggest modification of the points system:

It would be cool if students could do different tasks, gaining experience and progress levels, well, as in the game with an open world. For example, someone can take three projects for 500 points and get 1500 points, while others can gain experience with 15 tasks worth of 100 points. Well, it would be more fair for those who really study. And it would increase motivation.

We are reluctant to attribute motivation loss (Table 3) to the possible negative effect of gamification as this loss, based on the survey responses, can be due to a variety of reasons, e.g., an unwanted or unpopular programming language, the complexity of assignments, unfriendly treatment and the lack of professors.

We observed no evidence of negative attitudes towards cross-generation learning practices, instead, some students clearly value such a diverse learning environment:

... Plus the atmosphere, where the learning environment is heterogeneous both in terms of previous occupations and experiences and in terms of age, gives you the opportunity to interact with completely different people, which is also quite interesting and different from the university experience, where everyone is mostly your peers.

You meet people of different ages, with different backgrounds - you can talk to people you would not normally meet.

However, older students share fear on the career limitations due to old age or lack of knowledge:

In general I am happy with everything, only there is a fear that I will not be able to get a great internship because of my age and lack of higher education in IT (30 years).

Regarding the need of family-friendly learning environment, according to the survey responses, 70% of the respondents said they are not married, and 92% of the respondents have no children under 18. "Family" as a challenge has been reported by 48 (23%) survey respondents, 7 (15%) of them have under-age children. Notably, those program participants who reported being married, tend to have lower dropout rates: 17% in married vs 29% in not married. Since the group represents around 30% of the School female population, it might be worth considering their special needs and suggestions. Those having children particularly indicated the need for adjustment to be able to handle family issues:

I wish those having families were given time off to go home (a week a month) (34 years old, 4 kids)

More humane deadlines for moms (young children are often sick and not always with sick leave, and that needs to be taken into account!!!) (40 years old, 1 child)

Softer deadlines for people like me, I have to both work and take care of my baby, and I'm not of the right age to sit up at night anymore (40 years old, 1 child)

Thus, the investigated alternative model presents a viable solution to provide opportunity to enter IT career for more people and thus contribute to filling the gap in the labor market. Some particularities should be considered for attracting and retaining women in this alternative learning model.

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APPENDIX 1. Survey questions.

1. Specify your gender
2. Specify your intake (wave)
3. Please indicate the highest level of education you have received
4. Do you have any education (diplomas, certificates) in the field of IT?
5. What level of education (diplomas / certificates) do you have in the field of IT?
6. Do you have a higher or vocational secondary education in another education sector? If yes, please specify which one (not IT)?
7. Did you have any experience in the IT field before entering School 21?
8. How many years is your experience in the IT field?
9. Are you continuing your studies at School 21 now?
10. What level have you reached at School 21?
11. Evaluate how these characteristics correspond to the School 21 (Likert scale)
 - i. Interesting program
 - ii. Boosts hard skills
 - iii. Boosts soft skills
 - iv. Helps to establish connection with employers
 - v. Promotes the development of contacts with fellow students
 - vi. There is a creative atmosphere in the School
 - vii. Gives significant career prospects
 - viii. Allows you to solve real cases
12. Are there any other advantages in School 21 besides those mentioned above?
13. How much do you agree with the following statements about School 21? (Likert scale)
 - i. The school lacks other areas of specialization (for example, UX, project management)
 - ii. Only the female intake is needed
 - iii. Internships in women's teams are required
 - iv. More female mentors in IT are needed
 - v. The school needs to improve its infrastructure
 - vi. There is a lack of consulting on career opportunities in the Russian Federation and abroad
14. What are the greatest challenges for you at school (caused during training)?
15. Are there any other downsides or anything that needs to be changed in School 21, in addition to those mentioned above?
16. Specify the region of your permanent residence.
17. Specify the city of permanent residence.
18. How old are you?
19. What is your current marital status?
20. Do you have any minor children?
21. How many children do you have under the age of 18?
22. Write your suggestions and comments for the School 21.